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“A Study To Assess The Level Of Self-Esteem Among G.N.M 1st Year Students At Selected College Of Nursing Safedabad Barabanki (UP.)”

Nazia Zaidi¹, Anhika², Arpana Singh³, Asha Gautam⁴, Chhaya Gaur⁵, Divya⁶, Harish Kumar Prajapati⁷, Kamlesh Kushwaha⁸, Misba⁹, Neha Maurya¹⁰, Poonam Yadav¹¹, Reema Bharti¹², Reena Yadav¹³, Renu Gupta¹⁴, Saloni Verma¹⁵, Santosh Kumar¹⁶, Shikha¹⁷

¹Assistant Professor, ²⁻¹⁷Pbbsc Final Year Students

¹Mental Health Nursing Department

¹⁻¹⁷Hind college of Nursing

UP, India

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Abstract: The present study entitled “A study to assess the level of self- esteem among G.N.M 1st year Students at selected college of Nursing Safedabad – Barabanki.” The study was conducted with the objective to assess the level of self-esteem among GNM first year students and to associate the level of self-esteem with selected socio demographic variables. The researcher used descriptive research design. The research approach was quantitative approach. The study was conducted at Hind School & College of Nursing. 80 samples were selected by using non probability convenience sampling technique. The tool used were socio demographic profile and Rosenberg self esteem scale. In present study the level of self-esteem indicates overall level of self-esteem in which majority 69 students (86.25%) had normal self-esteem level, 11 students comes under the category of low self-esteem (13.75%) and no students was of high self-esteem. The study findings revealed that majority of nursing student 69 (86.45%) were of normal level self esteem and low self esteem 11 (13.75%) there was no significant association between the level of self-esteem with selected socio demographic variables at 0.05 level of significant. The study findings revealed that majority of nursing student 69 (86.45%) were of normal level self esteem and low self esteem 11 (13.75%) there was no significant association between the level of self-esteem with selected socio demographic variables at 0.05 level of significant.

Keywords: Assessment, General Nursing and Midwifery (GNM) Students, Nursing Students, Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale, Self-Esteem, Socio-Demographic Variables, Student Nurses.

INTRODUCTION:

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Self-esteem is the level of approval, acceptance and self worth in relation to self. Self-esteem, as defined by Coppersmith, includes four dimensions: personal self esteem, social self-esteem, academic self-esteem and parental self-esteem. Personal self-esteem is a detailed understanding of the value of oneself. Social self-esteem is the perception of the quality of their relationships with others.¹ Nursing is a job that requires mental health at desired levels. The results of the studies indicate that the mental health of nursing students, besides influencing studying and daily life, also has a profound effect on the quality of professional practice in the future, and the staying in the profession. Therefore, identifying factors that can affect mental health is

of special importance.² Self- esteem plays a significant role in the development of a variety of mental disorders. Self-esteem has been found to be the most dominant and powerful predictor of happiness and life satisfaction.³

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

“A study to assess the level of self- esteem among G.N.M 1st year Students at selected college of Nursing Safedabad – Barabanki.”

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the level of self-esteem among GNM first year students.
2. To associate the level of self-esteem with selected socio demographic variables.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

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Bhagora.H (2024) conducted a non-experimental survey design was used for this study to assess the level of self-esteem among Bsc Nursing students at Nursing Colleges of Udaipur, Rajasthan. The 100 samples were selected using non probability purposive sampling method. The tool consists of two sections. Section A consists of the demographic data and Section B consists of Rosenberg's self-esteem scale, a highly reliable scale, to assess the self-esteem was used in the study. The researcher concluded that majority of the samples had low range of self-esteem (66.1 %) score less than 15 followed by normal range of self-esteem (29.8 %) score between 15 to 25 and the least by high self-esteem i.e only 4.1 % score more than 25. And a counseling session booklet is made on self-esteem and this is provided to low level self-esteem samples.⁴

Dr. Praveen Subravgoudar (2024).: a non-experimental descriptive research design was used for this studying in Selected College of Nursing at Kolhapur. Quantitative survey approach was used for this study. The samples were selected for the study includes 100 1st year nursing students studying in D. Y. Patil College of Nursing by using non-probability simple random sampling technique. The reliability of the tool was established and the data was collected by using demographic data and modified Zung anxiety scale and modified self-esteem scale Result The level of anxiety among nursing 1st year nursing students was revealed that majority (57%) had average anxiety, 33% had high anxiety, 9% had low anxiety and no one had elevated anxiety in 1st year nursing students. The level of self-esteem among nursing 1st year nursing students was revealed that majority (79%) had an optimum, 19% had average 2% had high self – esteem and no one had poor level of self-esteem.⁵

Mr. Siddhartha Lodh- 2024 -conducted using quantitative research approach and descriptive research design to asses the level of self- esteem among 1st year nursing student nemcare institute of science ,mirza ,kamrup ,asam design. 110 samples were collected through convenient sampling method tool standardized rosenberg self-esteem scale was used techniques was circulation of standardized tool i.e. Rosenberg self esteem scale, was used. it consist of two parts. part 1: demograp techniques: circulation of

standardized tool i.e. Rosenberg self esteem scale, was used result nursing students i.e.102 (92.7%) have normal self-esteem level, 1 (0.91%) students have high self-esteem level, and 7 (6.36%) students have low self-esteem level. there was significant association of level of self-esteem with demographic variables i.e. age, caste, religion, type of family.⁶

METHODS

Research Approach-Research approach in present study is quantitative research.

Research Design-Descriptive Research Design

Research Variable-This study will be conducted by demographic variable.

Research Setting-The research will be conducted at Hind School & College of Nursing.

Population-Nursing students

Target Population-The target population for present study will be G.N.M. students.

Sample-

The sample for this study were G.N.M. students studying at Hind School and College of Nursing.

Sampling Technique -

In the present study non-probability convenient sample technique will be used in order to select the sample for the given sample frame and population.

Sample Size-

Sample size of the present study is 80 students at Hind School & College of Nursing.

Tool Of Data Collection-

Data collection tools are the questionnaire which contain items of following aspects:

Section A : Questions related to socio demographic variables such as age , gender, birth order, parenting style ,and socio economic status .

Section B :Tool used for data collection will be Rosenberg Self -Esteem Scale[RSE].

It is a 10 item scale measuring global self-worth by measuring both positive and negative feelings about the self.

* ROSENBERG SELF-ESTEEM SCALE *

Below is a list of statements dealing with general feelings about yourself. Complete these questions based upon your feelings in the past 6 weeks.

1.	On the whole, I am satisfied with myself	0	1	2	3
2.	At the times, I think I am no good at all.	0	1	2	3
3.	I feel that I have number of good qualities.	0	1	2	3
4.	I am able to do things as well as most other people .	0	1	2	3
5.	I feel I do not much have much to be proud of.	0	1	2	3
6.	I certainly feels useless at times.	0	1	2	3
7.	I feel that I am person of worth, at least on a equal plane with others.	0	1	2	3
8.	I wish I could have more respect myself.	0	1	2	3
9.	All in all, I am inclined to feel that I am failure.	0	1	2	3
10.	I take a positive attitude toward myself.	0	1	2	3

*** Scoring of Rosenberg scale ***

Strongly agree=3, Agree=2, Disagree=1, Strongly Disagree=0,.

Items with an asterisk are reverse scored. To calculate the total self -esteem score, sum the scores for the 10 items. The higher the score, the higher the self -esteem. ³²

Level of self esteem	Frequency	Percentage
High self esteem (26-30)		%
Normal self esteem (16-25)		%
Low self esteem (0-15)		%

RESULTS:

This chapter deals with analysis and interpretation of data to assess the level of self esteem among nursing students. The

data was computed using descriptive and inferential statistics based on the objectives of the study.

Organization of data

The data was analysed and interpreted under the following headings:

SECTION 1:Socio demographic variables of the students studying in GNM First year.

SECTION 2:Assessment of level of self esteem among GNM First year students.

SECTION 3:Associate between the level of self esteem with socio demographic variables.

SECTION -1

DESCRIPTION OF SOCIO DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE

Table:1 Table showing frequency and percentage distribution of samples according to socio demographic variables.

n=80

Demographic variable	Category	Frequency(f)	Percentage (%)
Age	17-21 year	67	83.75
	22-25 year	12	0.15
	>25 year	1	0.125
Gender	Male	09	0.1125
	Female	71	0.8875
Birth order	First	29	0.3625
	Second	17	0.2125
	Third	09	0.1125
	Fourth	14	0.175
	Fifth	06	0.75
	Sixth	05	0.0625
Parenting style	Permissive	40	0.5
	Authoritative	37	0.4625

	Neglect full	03	0.03
Socio economic status	10,000-20,000	48	0.6
	21,000-30,000	17	0.21
	31,000-40,000	13	0.16
	41000 and above	02	0.025

SECTION 2

Assessment of the self-esteem

Table2: Table showing the self-esteem level
n=80

Level of self esteem	Frequency (f)	Percentage(%)
High self esteem (26-30)	0	0
Normal self esteem (16-25)	69	86.25
Low self esteem (0-15)	11	13.75

Level of self-esteem

Figure 1: Pie chart shows the level of self-esteem among nursing students.

SECTION 3

ASSOCIATION BETWEEN LEVEL OF SELF ESTEEM WITH SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

n=80

S. No.	Demographic variable	High self esteem	Normal self esteem	Low self esteem	Df	Calculated value(x)	P value
1	Age						
	A)17-21 year	0	57	09	04	0.1893	9.49
	B)22-25 year	0	11	0			
	C)>25 year	0	01	0			
2	Gender						
	A)male	0	09	0	02	1.617	5.99
B)female	0	60	11				
3	Birth order						
	1)first	0	27	02	10	3.73	18.31
	2)second	0	14	03			
	3)third	0	08	01			
	4)forth	0	12	02			
	5)fifth	0	04	02			
6)sixth	0	04	01				
4	Parenting style						
	A)permissive	0	33	07	04	1.22	9.49
	B)authoritative	0	33	04			
	C)neglectful	0	03	0			
5	Monthly family income						
	A)10,000-20,000	0	43	05	06	9.15	12.59
	B)21,000-30,000	0	11	0			
	C)31,000-40,000	0	13	0			
	D)>40,000	0	02	0			
			6				

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DISCUSSION

This study assesses the level of self-esteem among G.N.M.1ST year students at Hind school and college of nursing safedabad-Barabanki (UP).

First objective

To assess the level of self-esteem among G.N.M.1st year students.

In present study the level of self-esteem indicates overall level of self-esteem in which majority 69 students (86.25%) had normal self-esteem level, 11 students comes under the category of low self-esteem (13.75%) and no students was of high self-esteem.

This study findings were consistent with the study conducted by **Nandan.L(2021)** The result shows that majority of the Nursing Students i.e. 59.2% have moderate level of self-esteem and 23.6% of the Nursing Students have high level of self-esteem.

This study findings were consistent with the study conducted by **Almansour mansoor.M(2023)** The findings revealed that 265 students (76.6%) had moderate self-esteem levels, 53 students (15.3%) had low self-esteem, and 28 students (8.1%) had high levels of self-esteem.

Second Objective

To associate the level of self-esteem among with selected demographic variables.

In present study, the results depicts that there was no association between level of self-esteem with selected sociodemographic variables age, gender, birth order, parenting style, monthly family income.

On other hand study conducted by **Nandan.L**, there was a significant association between two selected demographic variables i.e. gender and monthly family income of the Nursing Students with their level of self-esteem.

The study findings were consistent with the study conducted by **Mr. Siddhartha Lodh**. There was significant association between the level of self-esteem with demographic variables i.e. age, caste, religion, type of family.

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